

EFFECT OF PRESSURE ON THE IMPREGNATION OF THERMOPLASTIC RESIN INTO A UNIDIRECTIONAL FIBER BUNDLE

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ABSTRACT

Impregnation of molten thermoplastic resin into continuous unidirectional fiber tows was investigated. The degree of impregnation is defined as the ratio between the number of impregnated fibers and the total number of fibers of a tow. The degree of impregnation was modeled as a function of time, impregnation pressure, impregnation temperature and tow size assuming that the radial inward flow of resin through the fiber tow is governed by Darcy's law. The effect of the impregnation pressure on the permeability was studied. Experiments were performed to evaluate the validity of the model. Toray T300 graphite fiber bundles and PolyEtherEtherKetone (PEEK) resin were used. Pressure and temperature were applied to fiber tows surrounded with resin powder in a mold. After a predetermined time, the sample was taken out and the degree of impregnation was measured from the microphotographs of the cross-sections of samples. Experiments were performed for different impregnation conditions such as impregnation time, pressure, temperature and tow size. Good agreement was found between the model and the experimental data.

INTRODUCTION

Thermoplastic resins as matrix material for advanced composites have many advantages over thermosetting counterparts. Fracture toughness is very high compared to thermosetting resins. Since polymerization is complete, thermoplastic resins require no time for chemical reaction contrary to the thermosetting resins. There is no need for sub-zero temperature storage, and minor changes to shape are possible even after the manufacture. However, since the polymerization is finished beforehand, the viscosity of thermoplastic resin is very high. The high viscosity imposes many problems in the manufacturing process of composites. Difficulty in impregnation of resin into reinforcing fibers is one of the serious problems. Along with poor dispersion of fibers in the thermoplastic matrices, impregnation has been a major obstacle for thermoplastics being used as matrix material for advanced composites. Many semi-crystalline thermoplastics such as PEEK have no effective solvent and thus solution dip method in prepregging is not applicable for these class of materials. Moreover, since these thermoplastics usually have very high melting point close to decomposition temperature, reducing viscosity by raising process temperature has not been successful.

Lee and Springer [1] proposed a model describing the impregnation process in the absence of pressure. In order to speed up the impregnation, pressure must be applied. No research work so far is available regarding the effect of pressure on impregnation. Guceri [2] conducted numerical simulations of resin transfer molding process without considering the effect of applied pressure on the permeability of fiber mats. Therefore the objective of this study is to find out the effect of pressure on the impregnation of fiber bundle with thermoplastic resin matrices.

MODEL

Impregnation is accomplished by surrounding the fiber tow with the matrix and let the polymeric matrix penetrate into the fiber. To aid in the impregnation, temperature is kept as high as possible to reduce the viscosity of the resin. One way to accelerate the impregnation process is to apply pressure. As in the ideal case, if the fibers in the tow are perfectly straight and parallel to each other, the fiber bundle will collapse inward leaving no room for the resin to penetrate as pressure is applied. In the real situation, however, individual fibers are not perfectly straight. Rather it is wavy in nature. Therefore as the bundle collapses inward by the applied pressure, physical contacts between the fibers will take place at some points. In between these contact points there always exist rooms for the resin to pass through. The room between the fibers which is directly related to the permeability of the fiber bundle represents the resistance for resin flow. As the pressure increases the rooms between the fibers get smaller. Thus it can be stated that the permeability of the fiber bundle is a function of applied pressure.

If we assume that Darcy's law can be applied for the radial flow of the resin,

$$V_r = -\frac{K}{\mu} \frac{dP}{dr} \quad (1)$$

where V_r is the radial velocity of the resin, K is permeability, P is applied pressure and r designates the radial position (Fig.1). The rate of mass flow through the radial position r is

$$\dot{m} = \rho(-V_r)(2\pi r)\epsilon \quad (2)$$

where ϵ is the porosity of the fiber bundle. Equations (1) and (2) give

$$\frac{\dot{m}}{2\pi r \epsilon} \frac{dr}{r} = \frac{K}{\mu} dP \quad (3)$$

The pressure at $r=r_o$ is the applied pressure, i.e., P_o . Integrating Eq.(3) from r_o to r_f yields

$$\frac{\dot{m}}{2\pi r \epsilon} \ln\left(\frac{r_f}{r_o}\right) = -\frac{K}{\mu} (P_o - P_a) \quad (4)$$

where r_f is the location of the resin front where the pressure is the atmospheric pressure P_a . The mass flow rate can be expressed in terms of dr_f/dt as

$$\dot{m} = 2\pi \rho r_f \epsilon \left(-\frac{dr_f}{dt}\right) \quad (5)$$

Equations (4) and (5) yield

$$r_f \ln\left(\frac{r_f}{r_o}\right) dr_f = \frac{K}{\mu} (P_o - P_a) dt \quad (6)$$

Integrating Eq.(6) along with the initial condition ($r=r_o$ at $t=0$) gives

$$t = \frac{\mu r_o^2}{4K(P_o - P_a)} \left\{ 2\left(\frac{r_f}{r_o}\right)^2 \ln\left(\frac{r_f}{r_o}\right) + 1 - \left(\frac{r_f}{r_o}\right)^2 \right\} \quad (7)$$

The degree of impregnation D_{imp} can be defined as the ratio between the total number of fibers and the number of impregnated fibers. If we assume that fibers are distributed uniformly, the degree of impregnation can be expressed as

$$D_{imp} = \frac{\text{Area Impregnated}}{\text{Total Area}} = \frac{\pi r_o^2 - \pi r_f^2}{\pi r_o^2} = 1 - \left(\frac{r_f}{r_o}\right)^2 \quad (8)$$

Substituting Eq.(8) into Eq.(7), we finally obtain the degree of impregnation as a function of time, applied pressure, viscosity, initial bundle radius and permeability.

$$t = \frac{\mu r_o^2}{4K(P_o - P_a)} \{ 2(1 - D_{imp}) \ln \sqrt{(1 - D_{imp}) + D_{imp}} \} \quad (9)$$

The permeability of the fiber bundle decreases as pressure is increased. Gutowsky [3] proposed a model describing the relationship between the applied pressure and the volume fraction of fiber tow as

$$P_o - P_a = A \frac{\left(\sqrt{\frac{v}{v_o}} - 1\right)}{\left(\sqrt{\frac{v_a}{v}} - 1\right)^4} \quad (10)$$

where v, v_a, v_o are the volume fraction of fiber tow, the maximum available volume fraction of fiber tow and the initial volume fraction of fiber tow, respectively.

Once the volume fraction is known, permeability can be estimated by Carman-Kozeny equation [4]

$$K = \frac{R^2}{4k_{ii}} \frac{(1 - v)^3}{v^2} \quad (11)$$

where R is a radius of single fiber and k_{ii} is a Carman-Kozeny Constant. Gutowski [3] measured the value of K for graphite fiber tow. By fitting Eq.(11) to data, he obtained a value of k_{ii} for graphite fibers

$$k_{ii} = 17.9 \quad (12)$$

Combining Eqs.(10) and (11) permeability of fiber tow for different pressures can be calculated. Permeability of a graphite fiber tow as a function of pressure is shown in Fig. 2. As the fiber bundle collapses inward due to applied pressure, initial tow radius also changes. This change in the radius, Δ_r , is directly related to the change in volume fraction

$$\Delta_r = r_o \left(1 - \sqrt{\frac{v_o}{v}}\right) \quad (13)$$

Thus Eq.(9) can be rewritten as

$$t = \frac{\mu(r_o - \Delta_r)^2}{4K(P_o - P_a)} \{ 2(1 - D_{imp}) \ln \sqrt{1 - D_{imp}} + D_{imp} \} \quad (14)$$

where r_o is fiber tow radius without pressure and Δ_r is change in the tow radius by applied pressure.

Equation (14) along with Eqs.(10)-(13) provides a relationship between the degree of impregnation and the process variables in the impregnation process, namely impregnation pressure, temperature, tow size and time.

EXPERIMENTAL

Tests were performed to evaluate the validity of the model. In these tests Toray T300 graphite fiber tows (3K, 6K, 12K) were impregnated with PEEK 150P polymer. Prior to the tests the sizing was removed from the fibers by the following procedure. The fibers were immersed in methylethylketone (MEK) for 24 hours, then were washed with fresh MEK in an ultrasonic cleaner for 30 minutes. This procedure was repeated. After the second treatment with fresh MEK the fibers were dried in a vacuum oven at 80 °C for two hours. A fiber tow, treated in the above manner, was placed in a cavity of a matched die mold (Fig.3). The mold was made of steel and nickel was plated on the mold surface. The mold was filled with PEEK 150P powder to make the fiber tow surrounded by resin. The mold then was placed in a hot press and heated to the test temperature with no pressure applied. The mold was held at the test temperature for approximately 10 minutes with no pressure applied to reach the thermal equilibrium. Once the mold reached the test temperature, pressure was applied. After a preset period of time the mold was removed from the hot press and cooled to room temperature. The impregnated tow was removed from the mold, was cut perpendicular to the fibers, and the tow cross-section was examined with an optical microscope. The number of impregnated fibers in the tow was counted, and the degree of impregnation was calculated by the expression

$$D_{\text{imp}} = \frac{\text{Number of Impregnated Fibers}}{\text{Total Number of Fibers}} \quad (15)$$

This process was repeated for different pressures (2 atm, 4 atm, 5 atm and 10 atm), different temperatures (370 °C, 380 °C, 390 °C and 400 °C), different tow sizes (3K, 6K and 12K) and different duration of time (5,10,20, and 30 minutes). The data are shown in Fig.4-7.

The degree of impregnation was also calculated by the model (Eqs.10-14) for the test conditions. The following value and expression were used for the radius without pressure r_0 and the resin viscosity μ

$$r_0 = 400 \quad \mu\text{m} \quad \text{for 6K tow} \quad (16)$$

$$\mu = 1.13 \times 10^{-10} \exp\left(\frac{19123}{T(K)}\right) \quad \text{Pa} \cdot \text{sec}$$

where T is temperature.

Initial volume fraction v_0 (Eq.10) was taken to be 0.5 and the final volume fraction v_a was assumed to be 0.69 for poorly aligned fiber tows [3]. The value of constant A in Eq.(10) was determined by fitting the model to data. One data point from experiments was selected (10 atm, 20 minutes, 370 °C, 6K tow) for the fitting. The value of A was found to be

$$A = 4.4 \quad (17)$$

The results of the calculations by the model are presented in Fig.4-7. As can be seen the agreement between the model and experimental data is good, and this lends support to the validity of the model.

CONCLUDING REMARKS

A model is developed to predict the effect of pressure and other process variables on the impregnation of fiber tows. The model supplements the result obtained by Lee and Springer for the impregnation process in the absence of pressure [1].

The model assumes that the permeability of fiber tow is equal to the permeability of dry part of the tow. This assumption may not be valid if the penetrating path is long such as in resin transfer molding. In such a case, the permeability may be governed also by the pressure gradient, not just by absolute magnitude of pressure.

As the agreement between the model and the experimental data is good, the model presented here can be employed in analyzing and optimizing the impregnation process of thermoplastic matrix composites.

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Fig.1 Geometry of the Model

Fig.2 Effect of Pressure on the Permeability of Fiber Tow

Fig.3 Schematic of the Mold Used in the Impregnation Tests

Fig.4 Degree of Impregnation as a Function of Pressure. $T = 370^{\circ}\text{C}$, Tow Size = 6K and Impregnation Time = 30 Min. Experimental Data and Result of the Model. The Error Bars Represent the Spread of Data.

Fig.5 Degree of Impregnation as a Function of Temperature. $P = 10$ atm, Tow Size = 6K and Impregnation Time = 10 Min. Experimental Data and Result of the Model. The Error Bars Represent the Spread of Data.

Fig.6 Degree of Impregnation as a Function of Tow Size. $P = 10 \text{ atm}$, $T = 370^\circ \text{ C}$ and Tow Size = 6K. Experimental Data and Result of the Model. The Error Bars Represent the spread of Data.

Fig.7 Degree of Impregnation as a Function of Time. $P = 10 \text{ atm}$, $T = 370^\circ \text{ C}$ and Tow Size = 6K. Experimental Data and Result of the Model. The Error Bars Represent the Spread of Data.